

Towards Outliers-Resistant Optimization for SLAM

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Abstract—Pose Graph Optimization (PGO) is the problem of refining an initial estimate of a set of poses from a set of pairwise relative measurements. The optimization procedure can be significantly compromised, even by a single outlier, resulting in distorted results that have no meaning. Recent works on Robust Optimization build on top of classic solvers methods that can handle as many outliers as possible. This paper presents a method that approximates the solution to the combinatorial problem of finding the maximally consistent set of measurements in an incremental fashion. It is demonstrated on standards benchmarks that our method competes with or outperforms state-of-the-art methods at handling outliers while providing online performances.

Index Terms—Simultaneous Localization and Mapping, Robust Optimization, Outlier Detection

I. INTRODUCTION

The Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) problem is crucial in mobile robotics. Researchers have adopted a graphical representation for SLAM, where nodes represent robot positions, and edges capture spatial relationships with some noise. Pose Graph Optimization (PGO) uses this representation to address the non-convex maximum likelihood estimation problem in SLAM, finding the most consistent node configuration with the given constraints. Popular libraries like g2o [1], GTSAM [2], and Ceres [3] are commonly used for PGO.

To create a pose graph, a **front-end** component is required to generate spatial constraints. This work focuses on two key types of constraints: odometry constraints, linking consecutive poses, and loop closure constraints, connecting non-consecutive poses. Many methods assume these constraints have noise but no outliers. However, these assumptions only hold when being overly cautious, leading to reduced accuracy, or in controlled environments, limiting system applicability. Nevertheless, expecting the front end to always make correct assumptions based on isolated observations is unrealistic. Therefore, the responsibility for handling erroneous measurements should fall on the **back-end**, which has access to the complete exploration history.

Recent works on graph-based SLAM proposed stacking methods that are able to handle large amounts of outliers, such as RANSAC [4], GNC [5], Consensus-Maximization [6] [7] [8], and M-estimators [9], on top of classic solvers. Our contribution falls in the Consensus-Maximization category. Our method tries to approximate the solution to the combinatorial problem of finding the maximally consistent set of measurements in an incremental fashion achieving online

Fig. 1. Performances of the proposed method on, respectively, the INTEL, M3550, MIT and CSAIL datasets with 20% of outliers added.

performance, while the majority of methods are designed for offline usage.

II. METHOD

The proposed method is built on top of these assumptions and ideas:

- Odometry measurements are presumed to be inliers [10];
- The number of inliers grows at a faster rate compared to the outliers [6];
- Start from a simpler version of the problem, for which its solution will be meaningful for the more complex version of the problem [11];
- Reduce the nonlinearity of the problem as much as possible;
- Instead of rejecting outliers, reject non-consistent measurement.

The pose graph uses the nodes to represent the discretized poses of the robot, and the edges that connect the nodes represent the spatial relations between them. The full state can be represented using the vector $\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_n)$. Optimizing a pose graph translates to finding the nodes configuration that minimize the following cost function:

$$\mathbf{x}^* = \underset{\mathbf{x}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{(a,b) \in E} \mathbf{e}_{ab}(\mathbf{x}_a, \mathbf{x}_b)^T \Omega_{ab} \mathbf{e}_{ab}(\mathbf{x}_a, \mathbf{x}_b) \quad (1)$$

where the error is defined as follows :

$$\mathbf{e}_{ab}(\mathbf{x}_a, \mathbf{x}_b) = \mathbf{h}_k(\mathbf{x}_a, \mathbf{x}_b) \boxminus \mathbf{z}_k, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{h}_k(\mathbf{x}_a, \mathbf{x}_b)$ is the prediction function and \mathbf{z}_k is its relative observation. Following [12] we are going to divide

the set of constraints $E = E_o \cup E_l$, where E_o is the set of odometry measurements that represent constraints between non-consecutive poses, and E_l is the set that contains the loop closure measurements, that represent constraints between non-consecutive poses.

It allows us to rewrite the cost function in Eq.1 in the following manner :

$$\sum_{a \in E_o} \mathbf{e}_a(\mathbf{x}_a, \mathbf{x}_{a+1})^T \Omega_{a,a+1} \mathbf{e}_a(\mathbf{x}_a, \mathbf{x}_{a+1}) + \sum_{(a,b) \in E_l} \mathbf{e}_{ab}(\mathbf{x}_a, \mathbf{x}_b)^T \Omega_{ab} \mathbf{e}_{ab}(\mathbf{x}_a, \mathbf{x}_b) \quad (3)$$

The method aims to be deployed in online applications. That means that the graph is built incrementally and we are not able to exploit the full mission information like offline methods do. In order to be able to perform robust optimization with online performances, the first obstacle is to reduce to size of the problem as much as possible, instead of taking into account the full problem. Having a smaller size problem will guarantee better convergence because of less non-linearity and wider convergence basin, while also increasing the speed of convergence.

Upon receiving a loop closure candidate that relates the poses x_i and x_j the active portion of the graph is selected in the following manner :

- Initialize the set $E_{so} \in E_o$ with the odometry constraints between i and j ;
- Initialize the set $E_{sl} \in E_l$ with the accepted loop closure constraints that affect the region identified by the candidate;
- Eventually, augment the set E_{so} with possible additional odometry constraints introduced by the accepted loop closures.

An example of the selection of the active region of a graph is reported in Fig.4. The cost function relative to that subgraph can be defined as follows:

$$\sum_{a \in E_{so}} \mathbf{e}_a(\mathbf{x}_a, \mathbf{x}_{a+1})^T s \Omega_{a,a+1} \mathbf{e}_a(\mathbf{x}_a, \mathbf{x}_{a+1}) + \sum_{(a,b) \in E_{sl}} \mathbf{e}_{ab}(\mathbf{x}_a, \mathbf{x}_b)^T \Omega_{ab} \mathbf{e}_{ab}(\mathbf{x}_a, \mathbf{x}_b) + \mathbf{e}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j)^T \Omega_{ij} \mathbf{e}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) \quad (4)$$

where s is a scaling factor applied to the odometry constraints. We exploit the fact that the odometry measurements are outliers-free, adding weight to the constraints in order to guide the optimization to maintain local consistency. We do not try to identify outliers, but inconsistent measurements and to do so we check if the optimization was able to find a configuration of the nodes for which all the constraints pass the χ^2 test with $\alpha = 0.95$. If convergence was reached, than the candidate loop closure is added to the set of accepted loop closures, and the solution will be propagated to the rest of the nodes. Otherwise, the candidate is rejected and the state is reverted to what it was previous the optimization.

Fig. 2. The presented diagram shows the interested constraints that will participate in the acceptance procedure. The dotted red circle represents the subproblem of interest, the black edges represent odometry constraints, the green edges represent accepted loop closures and the red edge represents the candidate.

III. EXPERIMENTS

The proposed method, which will be referred to as VOT has been implemented in the g2o [1] framework. The Max-Mixture method [13], which will be referred to as MAX_MIX, has been implemented using the OpenSLAM implementation in g2o. Then the following methods, instead, were already used and provided by the gtsam library [2]. The Graduated Non-Convexity [5], Dynamic Covariance Scaling [14], and Huber [15], will be referred to respectively as GNC, DCS, and HUBER. For Pairwise consistent measurement set maximization method [6] it was used the implementation in Kimera [16].

A. Datasets

The datasets used for evaluation are currently the standard for evaluating the performances of back-end optimization and are described in [17] [18]. They can be divided into two categories, synthetic and real. The Intel, Mit, Csail, Freiburg Building, and Freiburg University Hospital datasets are real datasets, while M3500 is synthetic. In both cases, the datasets are free of outliers. The loop closure edges in the unaltered datasets were used as the ground truth for the inliers. In order to validate the different methods outliers were added using the Vertigo package [19]. Outliers were added as a percentage of the total inliers present in the dataset in order to have balanced results.

B. Evaluation

The amount of outliers added varies from 10% to 100% of the ground truth inliers, discretized every ten percent. For every outlier percentage, 10 different trajectories have been generated for fair testing. As done in [20], for methods that don't explicitly classify measurements, an inlier is defined as a measurement having a χ^2 error less than χ_{th}^2 at $\alpha = 0.95$. On average VOT is able to classify a measurement as consistent or non-consistent in $dt = 0.1498$ seconds. In order to compare s.o.a methods with the proposed method that is incremental, the measurements classified as inliers and outliers are compared at the end of the optimization of the full problem. One small note to take is that results for both GNC and PCM were taken after the result of a fixed number

TABLE I
EVALUATION OF THE ATE AND RPE OF THE DIFFERENT METHODS ACROSS ALL THE DATASETS PRESENTED.

	GNC		HUBER		DCS		MAXMIX		PCM		VOT	
	ATE	RPE	ATE	RPE	ATE	RPE	ARE	RPE	ATE	RPE	ATE	RPE
20	50.354	22.849	77.486	16.405	57.221	24.109	62.140	0.220	71.239	27.449	25.711	0.053
40	61.817	29.288	75.835	18.831	63.799	29.216	59.430	0.313	64.271	25.371	31.723	0.052
60	65.657	33.078	78.377	25.232	71.888	34.415	60.782	0.344	67.638	26.502	30.337	0.056
80	67.144	34.087	79.789	27.958	73.755	33.984	61.275	0.379	72.342	26.233	28.830	0.053
100	71.710	35.537	82.330	27.328	76.267	37.685	57.437	0.431	77.232	28.542	33.244	0.048

of iterations. It was done due to the large convergence time of the methods and the exhaustive amount of testing that was carried out for each method.

The precision is one of the most crucial parameters for a correct termination for the optimization. The precision has to be as close to one as possible because even small amounts of outliers can completely ruin the trajectory estimate. In Fig.3 we can notice that MAXMIX, VOT and PCM are the methods that reject the most outliers across the different datasets. While, for GNC it is likely that it wasn't able to reach convergence giving it similar results to DCS and GM. Even if the precision is high, if the recall is small that means that we are not including the constraints that will allow us to eliminate the drift accumulated from the odometry. Also having a low recall score will lead to poor trajectory estimation, but the acceptable bound is not as strict as the precision one. Here all methods are able to have almost constant performances across the different datasets for the different outlier percentages. The methods that are able to obtain the best recalls are ADAPT, GNC with VOT having slightly worse results.

The F1 metric, which relates both precision and recall together, is able to give a more global overview of the performances of each method. It can be seen in Fig.3 that the methods report a similar trend with respect to the precision, and it was expected given the pseudo-constant behavior of the methods for the recall. ADAPT dominates for smaller

percentage of outliers, while VOT is able to keep stable and reliable results for all the different percentages, resulting in having the best performances for a higher percentage of outliers.

Finally, Table I shows respectively the ATE and RPE metrics. We can see that for the ATE almost all methods have the same performances, while also not being the most meaningful metric to use in this case because the final result strongly depends on the type of distortion applied to the final trajectory. Instead, the RPE is able to reward at least local consistency of the trajectories facilitating the evaluation of the performances of the different methods more objectively. Here it can be seen that the best trajectory estimations were obtained by VOT and MAXMIX.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The reported results demonstrated that the proposed method is able to obtain performances that are comparable to or surpass state-of-the-art solutions at handling outliers while providing online performances. The shown results are results taken over different datasets while using the same parameters. So the proposed method has the ability to generalize better across different environments and its only control parameter is easy to set. Offline methods such as GNC, PCM will likely obtain better performances after the complex process of finding the correct parametrization. Currently, the proposed

Fig. 3. Overall performances of the different methods across all standard datasets.

method's greatest drawback is that the quality of the voting procedure is vulnerable when there is a long trajectory to consider and there are no strict voters that constrain that section of the trajectory. This is the scenario that leads to the most false positives. A possible future work direction would be to pair the proposed method with another one that is able to correct some wrong decisions, in order to have the advantages of both offline methods that are able to have a more global vision of the solution and the proposed method that is able to find a good approximation to the consensus set online.

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